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Master Thesis

LEGITIMATE INTEREST AS A LAWFUL BASIS FOR AI TRAINING: LIMITS, SAFEGUARDS AND GOVERNANCE

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1. Introduction¹

There is not enough human-generated data to feed Large Language Models (LLMs)². In fact, soon there won't be. In a paper published in June 2024th, scientists predicted that, if the current trend and fast development of LLMs continues, those models will be trained on all public human text data between 2026 and 2032. Maybe even sooner if the models are overtrained.³ It is no news that artificial intelligence (AI) models require vast amounts of text, images, and videos to be trained – this is even recognized in Recital 105 of the European Union Artificial Intelligence Act (EU AI Act)⁴. However, this “hunger” for data creates not only problems of data availability but also raises questions on the lawfulness of data processing when it comes to personal data.

That is because the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the gold standard when it comes to personal data, stipulates that any processing of personal data shall abide by principles (Article 5), being one of them the lawfulness of processing (Article 6). The regulation lays out six different possibilities, the so-called lawful basis – or legal basis – and those are: (a) consent; (b) performance of a contract; (c) legal obligation; (d) vital interest of the data subject or another natural person; (e) public interest; and (f) legitimate interest.⁵ Processing publicly available personal data to train AI models, being a processing activity like any other, is no exception. A legal basis must be chosen, and it must fit within its purposes of processing.

However, the choice is not so simple as it may seem. Although a case-by-case analysis is required, it is possible, on a high-level analysis, to pre-determine which legal basis may apply. Several data protection authorities (DPAs) have issued guidance on the matter and the UK DPA, Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) has even stated that legitimate interest is the “*only available lawful basis*”.⁶

¹ Footnotes compiled with the support of Artificial Intelligence. Tool used: ChatGPT. Model: 5. Date: 30/08/2025. Prompt: “Can you help me organize my Master thesis footnotes and bibliography based on OSCOLA? Here is a full list of footnotes. Please organize it and proof check if the formatting is correct. I also need that whenever a reference is repeating itself, this one is turned to *ibid*”.

² Large Language Models, also known as LLMs, are very large deep learning models that are pre-trained in vast amounts of data. These models are usually transformer-based and can learn patterns in language that they use to predict, understand, translate, or even code, based on the input prompts given by users. Models like ChatGPT (by the company OpenAI) are even multi-modal, and can create not only text, but images, and videos as well.

³ Pablo Villalobos and others, ‘Will we run out of data? Limits of LLM scaling based on human-generated data’ (arXiv:2211.04325 v2, 4 June 2024) <<https://arxiv.org/abs/2211.04325>> accessed 20 August 2025.

⁴ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 [2024] OJ L168/1, recital 105.

⁵ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 [2016] OJ L119/1.

⁶ Information Commissioner's Office, *The Lawful Basis for Web Scraping to Train Generative AI Models* (10 May 2024) <<https://ico.org.uk/about-the-ico/what-we-do/our-work-on-artificial-intelligence/response-to-the-consultation-series-on-generative-ai/the-lawful-basis-for-web-scraping-to-train-generative-ai-models/>> accessed 19 August 2025.

The massive scale of data necessary to appropriately train a system creates a challenge to collect enough data⁷, making it that most companies do not have access to such a considerable database internally. Consequently, the only solution was to resort to web scraping. Web scraping refers to the automated, often indiscriminate collection of large volumes of online data, including personal data, using bots. From a legal perspective this “solution” can be quite problematic. The lack of a relationship between the individuals (hereinafter referred to as data subjects) and the company collecting the data makes it difficult to implement certain legal bases, to provide transparency, and to fulfil data subject requests, while the indiscriminate data collection clashes with the principles of data minimization and data necessity. There are even concerns expressed in the *Meta v. Bundeskartellamt*⁸ that this type of massive data processing could lead to data subjects feeling as if their private lives were being continuously monitored, and a decrease in self-expression in virtual environments.⁹ Therefore, choosing a legal basis is not enough; a whole governance framework, with meaningful and targeted mitigation measures, must be put in place to address those issues.

Another unfortunate consequence of web scraping is that by processing such a large amount of data, companies such as OpenAI will inevitably process special category data as well, such as data related to political opinions or the health of data subjects.¹⁰ In GDPR, those types of data have a blanket prohibition of processing (Art. 9(1)), and can only move forward where, in addition to a regular Article 6 legal basis, exceptions are also in place (Art. 9(2)). Thus, a different analysis is necessary for those use cases.

Therefore, based on case law, DPAs guidelines, industry best practices, governance frameworks, and real-life scenario analysis, this thesis intends to answer the following questions:

- Can legitimate interest under Article 6(1)(f) GDPR serve as a lawful basis for training AI models on personal data?
- Considering that legitimate interest does not apply to special category data, what alternatives can be put in place for this type of processing?

⁷ European Cloud Federation, ‘Overfitting: A Conversation Starter for the Next Summer Party’ *EuroCloud News* (1 August 2024) <<https://eurocloud.org/news/article/overfitting-a-conversation-starter-for-the-next-summer-party/>> accessed 28 August 2025; European Commission, *Deep Dive into Artificial Intelligence and Data Ecosystems – Fundamental Rights, Ethics and Data Protection* (2023) <<https://data.europa.eu/sites/default/files/course/Deep-dive%20into%20artificial%20intelligence%20and%20data%20ecosystems%20-%20fundamental%20rights%2C%20ethics%20and%20data%20protection.pdf>> accessed 28 August 2025.

⁸ CJEU, Case C-252/21 *Meta v Bundeskartellamt* ECLI:EU:C:2023:537, judgment of 4 July 2023.

⁹ Taner Kuru, ‘Lawfulness of the Mass Processing of Publicly Accessible Online Data to Train Large Language Models’ (2024) 14(4) *International Data Privacy Law* 326.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*

- Which mitigation measures (including obligations under the AI Act) should be implemented for a privacy compliant governance framework?

On the other hand, it is also important to highlight that this work will not cover:

- Regulations and jurisprudence outside of the EU regulatory framework;
- Sectoral laws;
- Personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences;
- Children’s personal data.

Chapter 1 will cover the legal foundation of legitimate interest and the best theoretically available, by: (i) analyzing Article 6 (1) legal basis and its applicability to the proposed use case; (ii) assessing real-life scenarios and case law on the matter. Chapter 2 will go into processing special category data, which includes: (i) debating whether all data collected via web scraping should be considered special category data; (ii) analyzing CJEU C-136/17¹¹ judgment and its applicability to training LLMs; (iii) diving deeper into the data manifestly made public exception. Lastly, the author will propose a governance model that fits with the three-step test requirements with a series of technical and organizational measures to be put in place by the data controller: (i) data minimization and filtering; (ii) transparency and documentation; (iii) data subject rights.

2. Lawful basis for AI training

Article 6(1) of GDPR revolves around the lawfulness of processing. This means that personal data processing can only be lawful if one of the six legal bases contained therein applies to the processing activity in question. There is no such thing as hierarchy among them, so a controller or processor should pick whatever aligns best and provide proper documentation justifying the choice made.¹² For the purposes of this work, the applicability of the legal basis will be analyzed in the order they are presented by the EU data protection law and based on the following use case:

¹¹ CJEU, Case C-136/17 *GC and Others v CNIL* (Grand Chamber, 24 September 2019).

¹² European Data Protection Board, *Guidelines 1/2024 on Processing of Personal Data based on Article 6(1)(f) GDPR (Legitimate Interest)* (Version 1.0, 8 October 2024). See also Opinion of AG Szpunar in Case C-394/23 *Mousse* ECLI:EU:C:2024:610, paras 28–29.

Controller collecting large scale datasets of ordinary personal data¹³ from the internet and using it to train a general-purpose LLM.

2.1 Consent (Art. 6(a))

The first legal basis to consider is consent (Art. 6(1)(a)). Although this option is designed to give individuals control over how their personal data is used, it is nearly impossible to implement in this scenario. The problem here is three-fold. First, due to the sheer amount of data subjects and high degree of automation; the lack of contact between data subjects and controller; difficulties in identifying those individuals and giving them the right to withdraw consent, it becomes practically impossible to obtain and manage that consent. Second, using consent could increase the likelihood of a system producing biased results, such as in a scenario where an AI system to route emergency calls to first responders quicker, but all individuals of a specific race or gender withheld consent.¹⁴ Third, the societal angle. In a research study requested by the non-profit organization None of Your Business (NOYB), individuals were asked whether they would like Meta to use their social media data to train the company's AI model. 66% of the participants stated they did not want Instagram, not Facebook using their data for such purposes. While 27% had nothing forward or against it, a mere 7% of participants actively wanted to have their data used.¹⁵

FIGURE 1. NOYB SURVEY ON USER ATTITUDES TOWARDS META'S USE OF PERSONAL DATA FOR AI TRAINING (2024)

¹³ Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens, *What are personal data?* (4 months ago [or approximate publication date]) <<https://www.autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl/en/themes/basic-gdpr/privacy-and-personal-data/what-are-personal-data>> accessed 30 August 2025. Ordinary personal data shall be understood, residually, as anything that is not categorized as special category data, in accordance with Art. 9(1) GDPR.

¹⁴ IAPP, 'A Legitimate Interest in AI Training' (30 December 2024) <<https://iapp.org/news/a/a-legitimate-interest-in-ai-training>> accessed 20 August 2025.

¹⁵ noyb, 'noyb Survey: Only 7 % of Users Want Meta to Use Their Personal Data for AI' (7 August 2025) <<https://noyb.eu/en/noyb-survey-only-7-users-want-meta-use-their-personal-data-ai>> accessed 30 August 2025

These results reflect a tendency that has been growing ever since Meta's new AI policy was announced. The policy led several major news outlets¹⁶ and Reddit discussion forums¹⁷ to question the data processing and consequently to guide people through the process of opting out of data processing. The public outcry was considerable, even among people who are not tech savvy or privacy aware. The results were clear: society is not willing to relinquish their data for LLM providers to train their models.

A similar situation happened with businesses. Many companies blocked their employees' access to free AI models to avoid leakage of internal confidential information¹⁸, and enterprise model licenses were purchased with promises of no use of data to re-train the AI models. This data shows that while companies want the benefits this technology brings, they do not want to trade off their business secrets in order to get it. This is one of the reasons why many companies opted to quietly change their terms of service to allow such training¹⁹, well aware that this business practice was frowned upon. Until AI companies are able to persuade society that the benefits of AI training outweigh the risks, consent will not be operational at this scale, even if there is a compliant and feasible way to implement consent management.

Noteworthy, that even if consent was used to collect personal data in the first place (e.g. pictures of employees taking during a company event for communication purposes and later posted on LinkedIn by the company's social media team), further processing of said personal data to train an AI model constitutes purpose creep and its is not compatible with the initial consent collected. Certainly, that data subject was not informed of that type of data processing when they gave consent. Even in a situation where the data controller itself decides to "automatize" an old process to make it more efficient, if said processing involves the use of

¹⁶ Euronews, 'Meta is About to Use Europeans' Social Posts to Train its AI: Here's How You Can Prevent It' (13 May 2025) <<https://www.euronews.com/next/2025/05/13/meta-is-about-to-use-europeans-social-posts-to-train-its-ai-heres-how-you-can-prevent-it>> accessed 19 August 2025; MIT Technology Review, 'How to Opt Out of Meta AI Training' (14 June 2024) <<https://www.technologyreview.com/2024/06/14/1093789/how-to-opt-out-of-meta-ai-training/>> accessed 19 August 2025; The New York Times, 'Meta's AI Scraping Policy' (13 May 2024) <<https://www.nytimes.com/article/meta-ai-scraping-policy.html>> accessed 19 August 2025; Wired, 'How to Stop Your Data from Being Used to Train AI' (27 June 2023) <<https://www.wired.com/story/how-to-stop-your-data-from-being-used-to-train-ai/>> accessed 19 August 2025.

¹⁷ Reddit, 'Filling Objection Form to Meta Using Your Data for AI Training' (22 April 2024) <https://www.reddit.com/r/facebook/comments/1cyevqw/filling_objection_form_to_meta_using_your/> accessed 19 August 2025; Reddit, 'Ne engedjétek, hogy a Meta AI tanításra használja [Do not allow Meta to use your data for AI training]' (9 June 2024) <https://www.reddit.com/r/hungary/comments/1k3vj01/ne_engedj%C3%A9tek_hogy_a_meta_ai_tan%C3%ADt%C3%A1sr_a_haszn%C3%A1lja/?tl=en> accessed 19 August 2025.

¹⁸ Siladitya Ray, 'Samsung Bans ChatGPT and Other Chatbots for Employees after Sensitive Code Leak' *Forbes* (2 May 2023) <<https://www.forbes.com/sites/siladityaray/2023/05/02/samsung-bans-chatgpt-and-other-chatbots-for-employees-after-sensitive-code-leak/>> accessed 30 August 2025.

Noor Al-Sibai, 'Amazon Bids Employees Not to Leak Corporate Secrets to ChatGPT' *Futurism* (25 January 2023) <<https://futurism.com/the-byte/amazon-bids-employees-chatgpt>> accessed 30 August 2025.

¹⁹ Federal Trade Commission, 'AI and Other Companies Quietly Changing Your Terms of Service Could Be Unfair or Deceptive' (6 February 2024) <<https://www.ftc.gov/policy/advocacy-research/tech-at-ftc/2024/02/ai-other-companies-quietly-changing-your-terms-service-could-be-unfair-or-deceptive>> accessed 19 August 2025.

AI, another, separate consent must be collected. This is also the position of the French Data Protection Authority (DPA), *Commission Nationale de l'Informatique et des Libertés* (CNIL).²⁰

2.2 Performance of a contract (Art. 6(1)(b))

Performance of a contract (Art. 6(1)(b)) is also not possible in a web scraping scenario, as the controller has no direct relationship with the data subjects, let alone a contract. Such standing is also shared by the French and Italian DPAs. In 2023, the Italian DPA banned ChatGPT's use in Italy due to lack of compliance with data protection law. One of the imposed conditions for reinstating services in the country was that OpenAI changed the legal basis used for collecting personal data for AI training from performance of a contract to either legitimate interest or consent.²¹ According to the Italian DPA contract as a legal basis was only fitted for processing of personal data of ChatGPT users, with whom OpenAI had a direct relationship, to enable performance of their services on a contractual basis.

2.3 Other legal basis (Art. 6(1)(c)(d)(e))

There is a group of legal bases that is hardly ever mentioned by EU DPAs when discussing AI training for general-purpose LLMs. These are:

- Legal obligation (Art. 6(1)(c));
- Vital interests of a data subject (Art. 6(1)(d));
- Performance of a task for the public interest or in the exercise of official authority (Art. 6(1)(e)).

This is mainly because of the use of their incompatibility with such a broad type of processing. Additionally, the term “necessary” in the text of the law, makes it a threshold difficult to achieve.

Legal obligation for example, legislations are area specific and cover particular topics e.g. data protection; AI governance; competition; medical devices. Therefore, a sole regulation will never provide enough justification for an LLM provider to process all the types of datasets required to properly train an AI model. It may be that using a general-purpose model as a baseline and subsequently fine-tuning it for a specific purpose and use case, can trigger the

²⁰ Commission nationale de l'informatique et des libertés (CNIL), 'Assurer que le traitement est licite' (2024) <<https://www.cnil.fr/fr/assurer-que-le-traitement-est-licite>> accessed 19 August 2025.

²¹ Garante per la protezione dei dati personali, 'Provvedimento del 11 aprile 2023 (9874702)' (11 April 2023) <<https://www.garanteprivacy.it/web/guest/home/docweb/-/docweb-display/docweb/9874702#english>> accessed 19 August 2025.

applicability of legal obligation as a legal basis e.g. a medical device (sensor) connected via API²² to a GPT model, and where the analysis done by AI is necessary to fulfil a notification requirement of a medical device regulation. However, this use case is out of scope of this assessment. Additionally, legislations are often agnostic regarding which method and technologies should be used for a specific type of processing. This is so they can be future-proof and flexible. While this can be advantageous in the sense that legislations do not need to be rewritten and reworded whenever a new technology comes by (e.g. Microsoft office, AI), on the other hand, it becomes nearly impossible to justify a processing under legal obligation.²³ Automatizing an already existing process (and training a tool to do it) for efficiency gains is positive, but will likely not be considered necessary to fulfil a legal obligation.

Vital interests of a data subject face a similar issue. This legal basis is deeply connected to life-or-death situations, which would require only quite a narrow scope of processing. Even taking into consideration scenarios of humanitarian purpose, or monitoring epidemics that have a broader scope, a general-purpose AI model would not be the most suitable tool. Again, a fine-tuned system, re-trained for a specific use case could perhaps rely on this legal basis (e.g. coronavirus monitoring app), but not the initial general-purpose model.

Performance of a task for the public interest or in the exercise of official authority (Art. 6(1)(e)) is also quite restrictive. It is often used for research, clinical trials, and statistics. It is also not compatible with a general-purpose model with large commercial models as ChatGPT. In its guidelines, the French DPA brings some possible applications, but they are all specific use cases, rather than general-purpose ones e.g. researches from a public research laboratory on the French language want to analyze the evaluation of the use of the language online, and for that they process data from comments published online from social networks (anonymized at short notice) to train a model that automatically detects the occurrence of certain expressions or spelling forms.²⁴

2.4 Legitimate interest (Art. 6(1)(f))

2.4.1 Main elements

Residually, all that is left is legitimate interest (Art. 6(1)(f)). However, this does not mean legitimate interest is the correct legal basis by default. In fact, EDPB is clear when saying that

²² An application programming interface (API) is a standardised way for one piece of software to request data or services from another, using agreed commands and formats, without direct access to the other system's internal code.

²³ Ibid (n 20).

²⁴ Ibid (n.20).

legitimate interest should not be seen as a last option if no other legal bases apply, nor should it be a preferred option because it might be considered less restrictive than the other Article 6(1) legal basis. It is not an open door to legitimizing any type of processing activities.²⁵ Thus, the position of whether it can be applicable should be carefully examined.

According to EDPB, there are three cumulative elements that must be fulfilled so legitimate interest can be used as a legal basis²⁶:

- First: the pursuit of a legitimate interest by the controller or by a third party;
- Second: the processing must be necessary for the pursuit purposes;
- Third: data subjects' rights and freedoms do not prevail over the legitimate interests. So, a balancing exercise must be performed;

For an interest to be legitimate, the purpose must be lawful. Therefore, it cannot be linked to an activity that is illegal in a country e.g. processing personal data for gambling; or to data obtained illegally e.g. from data brokers that failed to get consent when collecting a dataset. Some scholars, such as Waltraut Kotschy, go even beyond and state that a sole commercial interest, even though lawful, cannot be considered a legitimate interest:

*“In contrast to the antecedent provision in Article 7(f) DPD, ‘legitimate interest’ in the GDPR refers only to interests of private sector controllers. (...) A ‘legitimate interest’ is an interest which is visibly, although not necessarily explicitly, recognised by law, more precisely by Union or Member State law. Mere commercial interests will not suffice to establish a ‘legitimate interest’.”*²⁷

In alignment with Kotschy's position, until 2024, the Dutch DPA, was also of the opinion that purely commercial interests were insufficient as legitimate interest, with a caveat that legitimate interest may be established if an organization had an additional legally recognized interest, such as improving systems for fraud prevention or information technology security. Due to this strict position, their guideline defended that web scraping was virtually never

²⁵ European Data Protection Board, *Guidelines 1/2024 on Processing of Personal Data under Article 6(1)(f) GDPR (Legitimate Interest)* (Version 1.0, 8 October 2024) <https://edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2024-10/edpb_guidelines_202401_legitimateinterest_en.pdf> accessed 20 August 2025.

²⁶ Ibid.

²⁷ Christopher Kuner and others (eds), *The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): A Commentary* (OUP 2020; online edn, Oxford Academic) <<https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198826491.001.0001>> accessed 23 August 2025.

lawful, which included scraping for training AI models.²⁸ However, in light of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) decision in case C-621/22 *Tennisbond v. AP*, where it was determined that commercial interests can be configured as a legitimate interest,²⁹ the Dutch DPA reverted its previous opinion and issued a new guideline in April 2025 reflecting this position.³⁰ Noteworthy that EDPB also favours a more flexible approach for a case-by-case evaluation³¹, which strengthens the case for web scraping and AI training.

In this context, another important aspect to consider is that training AI models is not an end purpose in itself. For example, scientists may train an AI model to use x-ray images to detect cancer cells. Here, the goal is to detect cancer cells, not train AI. The same goes for a bank that trains an AI system to detect fraud. The end goal here is to detect fraud; training AI is just part of the process and a tool that will be required to achieve this goal.³² For general-purpose models, this might seem murkier, but one could say the purpose is to create a system with broad capabilities that can later be applied to many different tasks. It could be fine-tuned to detect cancer cells, to detect fraud, or to screen job applications. Generative AI chatbots could be defined as a means to enable its users to access information quickly and in a more digestible manner. The purpose defined at the end of this exercise will be the one that needs to be evaluated in the three-step test for legitimacy, which is key for an accurate and a fair Legitimate Interest Assessment (LIA).

It is, however, not enough that the interest is legitimate. It must also be necessary. Assessing necessity involves evaluating whether the purpose pursued cannot reasonably be achieved by other means less restrictive to fundamental rights and freedoms of data subjects.³³ On that point, one may argue that certain processes existed in the past and did not use AI, therefore, using AI would not be considered necessary for that processing. However, on the same note, email did not exist many years ago and still people had ways to communicate (e.g. via mail, fax, phone); same goes for the Microsoft Word, people could use typewriters to get their messages across. By adding new tools and technologies to those processes they became

²⁸ Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens, 'AP: Scraping bijna altijd illegaal' (1 May 2024)

<<https://autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl/actueel/ap-scraping-bijna-altijd-illegaal>> accessed 20 August 2024.

²⁹ Case C-621/22 *Koninklijke Nederlandse Lawn Tennisbond v Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens* ECLI:EU:C:2024:858.

³⁰ Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens, *Handreiking scraping door particulieren en private organisaties* (2 April 2025)

<<https://www.autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl/documenten/handreiking-scraping-door-particulieren-en-private-organisaties>> accessed 30 August 2025.

³¹ European Data Protection Board, *Report of the Work Undertaken by the ChatGPT Taskforce* (23 May 2024)

<https://www.edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2024-05/edpb_20240523_report_chatgpt_taskforce_en.pdf> accessed 20 August 2025.

³² IAPP (n 14).

³³ EDPB (n.25)

much more efficient, to the point that businesses could no longer work without them. They became necessary and in 2025 no one would dare question whether email is a business need or not. The same rationale can, therefore, be applied to AI. Even in such a short time frame – from 2022 to 2025 – many company’s internal processes and products can no longer function without AI, as this would decrease efficiency to an unacceptable standard. Nevertheless, this does not mean that all processes need an AI feature. In the end, it will be up to the controller to evaluate if from a business standpoint this feature is required, and then properly document and justified its choice and rationale.

Moreover, even if a processing involving AI training is legitimate and proven to be necessary, it cannot be implemented if it infringes fundamental rights and freedoms of data subjects. There must be a balance between the interest of the controller and the rights and freedoms on the data subjects. This is called a balancing test or balancing exercise, and it depends on the circumstances of each individual case.³⁴ A LIA must be performed and where required tangible mitigation measures must be put in place, such as: (i) data minimization principle; (ii) transparency principle; (iii) data subject rights. These measures will be discussed in further detail on chapter 4.

Finally, when companies already have a process for a specific type of data processing with a clear purpose and then decide to integrate AI to improve that process, the purpose of processing does not change. However, the introduction of AI adds a new tool that may bring significant new risks and consequences for data subjects, requires a new legal basis evaluation. Therefore, while this AI training cannot be considered further processing in accordance with Art. 6(4), GDPR, if after the re-evaluation the applicable legal basis is still legitimate interest, a controller can re-use their original LIA as a template and build up an updated one, reflecting the new status quo and appropriate safeguards are put in place to mitigate the additional risks.³⁵

2.4.2 Web scraping personal data

Therefore, it has been established that implementing this legal basis properly requires a significant amount of work and compromises. Not all data can be processed relying on it. Not every feature can be rolled out based on it. Yet, it was the choice of every major LLM provider for processing publicly available personal data for training their AI models in the EU. Looking at industry standard practices, the table below compiles the approach used by four LLM

³⁴ EDPB (n.25)

³⁵ IAPP (n 14).

providers (i) OpenAI – ChatGPT; (ii) Google – Gemini; (iii) Meta (Llama 3); (iv) Anthropic – Claude.³⁶

Provider	Use of publicly available data for training	Legal basis for processing (EU/EEA)	Where to find the information
OpenAI (ChatGPT)	“collect[s] publicly available information from the internet” to develop and improve models.	Legitimate interests (“we base our collection and use of publicly available information on legitimate interests under privacy laws like the GDPR”).	OpenAI Help Center, Our approach to data from the public web.
Google (Gemini)	“We use publicly accessible sources to help train Google’s AI models.”	Legitimate interests for “processing information from publicly accessible sources and your Gemini Apps information so that we can provide, maintain, improve, and develop Google products, services, and machine-learning technologies.”	Google Privacy Policy (general statement on training sources); Gemini Apps Privacy Hub (EU/UK legal bases section).
Meta (Llama 3)	Meta explains it will use public posts from Facebook and Instagram to train “AI at Meta.”	Legitimate interests explicitly named as the legal basis for using certain first-party data to train generative AI models.	Meta Newsroom (UK/EU rollout updates referencing the legal basis and public-post sources).
Anthropic (Claude)	Privacy Policy lists training sources including “Publicly available	Legitimate interests (listed under “Legal Bases for Processing” for purposes that include improving the Services and conducting research, the	Anthropic Privacy Policy (Section “Personal data we collect or receive to train our models” and Section

³⁶ Table compiled by AI. Tool used: ChatGPT. Model: 5. Date: 21/08/2025. Prompt: “I want to do a practical analysis of EU Privacy Policies of major LLMs providers. This includes ChatGPT, Gemini, Claude, Llama 3, etc. Can you provide in a table (with sources) on what are the legal basis being used for data collected from publicly available sources to train their model and where to find this in their policies?”.

	information via the Internet.”	bucket Anthropic uses for model development).	10 “Legal Bases for Processing”). Anthropic Help Center article on web crawling.
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This is not simply a one-sided or residual choice, nor a trend from the industry. Relying on legitimate interest is, for AI training, a good match, as it is compatible with its broad scope of processing. This also aligns with the positioning of several EU DPAs (e.g. ICO, Garante, CNIL, EDPB)³⁷, as they also describe legitimate interest as a possible fit for training AI models. The major point of contention here is whether those companies performed a strong LIA and implemented guardrails to address the GDPR principles as a whole. Thus, it is paramount to have a robust governance framework and a well-thought-out set of feasible and practical technical and organizational measures.

2.4.3 Re-purposed data from company databases

For the purposes of this work, the applicability of legitimate interest in the following use case will also be analyzed:

Controller re-purposes a large scale of ordinary personal data from the company’s databases (e.g. CRM and social media) and uses it to train a general-purpose LLM.

This additional analysis is required, because having a direct relationship with a data subject has a significant impact (and benefits) on what measures a controller needs to take to comply with GDPR. It becomes much easier to reach out to the data subject to notify them of upcoming changes to processing activities (e.g. via email, pop-up in apps, update of privacy notice) and fulfilling data subject requests. Nevertheless, that does not mean the controller has an easy task. This tension is starkly illustrated by Meta, whose repeated reliance on users’ personal data to train AI models has not only triggered multiple court proceedings but also exposed how fragile the legitimate interest basis can become when stretched to justify large-scale, high-risk processing.

In March 2024, Meta informed its leading DPA, the Irish Data Protection Commission (DPC), of its plans to train its LLMs using public content shared by adults on Facebook and Instagram across the EU/EEA. The initial proposal by Meta was met with concerns. Although

³⁷ ICO (n 6); Garante (n 21); CNIL (n 20); EDPB (n 31)

DPC did not publicize what these initial concerns were, they led Meta, in June 2024, to suspend their plans to train their LLM using personal data from EU/EEA residents.³⁸ Additionally, DPC also requested EDPB to develop a formal GDPR Opinion on the topic.³⁹ The Opinion, applicable to any LLM provider, contained several mitigation measures, and served as foundation for Meta to rethink your practices. The following improvements were implemented⁴⁰:

- Updating transparency notices to include specific notifications about the training;
- Updated an easier objection form;
- Longer notice period for users to change their profiles from public to private;
- Ensuring objection forms worked in-app and in all jurisdictions across Europe;
- Making sure the objection form was accessible for over a year;
- De-identification, filtering of data sets and output filters;
- Updated risks assessments such as LIA, Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIA) and Compatibility Assessments.

Despite those additional measures put in place, entities still had concerns and reservations regarding this data processing for AI training. As a result of that, in May 2025, a German Consumer Rights Organization (Verbraucherzentrale NRW) filed an emergency injunction with the Higher Regional Court of Cologne to stop Meta’s AI training plans. However, to the surprise of many, the court ruled that the legal basis of legitimate interest indeed applied, that all three steps were fulfilled, and stated that⁴¹:

"there is no other meaningful alternative for Meta to pursue and achieve its interests equally effectively by other, milder means. Meta has reviewed "considered available alternative ways" that would allow for less intensive use of personal data"

Furthermore, Meta was not the only company to receive a positive court decision regarding model training activities. Back in 2020, a data subject filed a complaint with the Belgian DPA, under allegations that a bank was using its personal data, including the content of payment

³⁸ DPC, ‘The DPC’s Engagement with Meta on AI’ (14 June 2024) <<https://www.dataprotection.ie/en/news-media/latest-news/dpcs-engagement-meta-ai>> accessed 29 August 2025.

³⁹ European Data Protection Board, *Opinion 28/2024 on Certain Data Protection Aspects Related to the Processing of Personal Data in the Context of AI Models* (18 December 2024) <https://edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2024-12/edpb_opinion_202428_ai-models_en.pdf> accessed 20 August 2025.

⁴⁰ Data Protection Commission (Ireland), ‘DPC Statement on Meta AI’ (14 June 2024)

<<https://www.dataprotection.ie/en/news-media/latest-news/dpc-statement-meta-ai>> accessed 20 August 2025.

⁴¹ *Verbraucherzentrale NRW eV v Meta Platforms Ireland Ltd* (Oberlandesgericht Köln, 23 May 2025) 15 UKI 2/25, ECLI:DE:OLGK:2025:0523.15UKL2.25.00 (NRWE).

transactions, to build models for their ‘personalized discounts’ service.⁴² The controller claimed to be using legitimate interest for this processing and that the models constitute further processing. On the matter of the legal basis, the DPA evaluated whether the three cumulative conditions for legitimate interest had been fulfilled. Regarding the first requirement, the court decided that the interest was legitimate since building those models were built in order to offer personalized discounts to the customers, which was part of the controller’s positioning in the market, responding to societal evolutions and trends such as digitalization, personalization and diversification of service. Regarding the second, it concluded that the analysis of transaction data was necessary to provide personalized discounts. Lastly, on the matter of data subjects’ rights and freedoms, the court concluded that there were enough mitigation measures in place, such as removal of identifiers, no sharing of data to third parties, no special category data processed, proper transparency provided via privacy policy and direct information to the customers, and right to opt-out (which the data subject did and was granted).⁴³ Although that use case was about a data model, many of its considerations can be applied to more modern AI models.

While both these cases were favorable to the controllers, the crucial difference between them were the mitigation measures. In the Belgian case, the bank implemented significant measures that dramatically decreased the risk score of this type of processing, while Meta implemented what could be considered as “bare minimum” measures, to show that something was done to improve its case. Although the measures proposed by Meta after negotiations with DPC were a welcoming improvement, there are less intrusive ways Meta could have approached this processing, for example:

- Instead of an opt-out mechanism, it should have been provided an opt-in mechanism for all legacy data that were processed in their social network before their policy change;
- For personal data processed in the tool after the policy change, an opt-out could then be an appropriate measure;
- A transition period between the policy change of at least 6 months for users to adjust and decide if they want to leave the platform or delete their data;

⁴² Personalized discount services are marketing practices where companies use individual customers’ data such as purchasing or transaction histories to generate tailored promotional offers or discounts.

⁴³ APD/GBA (Belgium) – 46/2024 (Litigation Chamber of the Belgian Data Protection Authority, 15 March 2024) DOS-2019-05837, GDPRhub <[https://gdprhub.eu/index.php?title=APD/GBA_\(Belgium\)_-46/2024](https://gdprhub.eu/index.php?title=APD/GBA_(Belgium)_-46/2024)> accessed 20 August 2025.

- The information notice about the change should have included a direct link to a simplified opt-out request form for new data processed, as well a link to a Trust Center containing the LIA, DPIA and Compatibility Assessments.

In summary, legitimate interest can apply to those use cases as well, but again, only if the controller properly addresses all GDPR principles and apply appropriate and significant mitigation measures.

3. Processing special category data

3.1 Should all data collected via web scraping be considered special category data?

The legal basis analysis, however, carries an additional layer of complexity. This is because whenever there is processing of special category data⁴⁴ Art. 6 needs to be applied in conjunction with Art. 9 GDPR. This is true for any processing of special category data, and using personal data to train LLMs is no exception. Therefore, a proper legal basis needs to be put in place, as well as an Art. 9(2) exception, as those two are supplementary to each other.⁴⁵ Special category data processing is more restrictive, because it could have a more significant impact on the data subject's rights and freedoms, such as a higher probability of discrimination or harm. For that reason, processing of this type of personal data is prohibited, unless one of Art. 9 (2) exception applies.

This is not usually a problem, as in a standard scenario a controller would simply link ordinary personal data with an Article 6 legal basis and link the special category data in a separate processing activity with an additional Article 9(2) exception. However, again, the automated and indiscriminate dataset collected through web scraping makes it virtually impossible to separate and classify the personal data into two different categories. This leads to two antagonistic positions within scholars:

1. Data collected *en bloc* containing both special category data and ordinary data shall be considered special category data in its entirety, to protect the data subject to stricter limitations⁴⁶;

⁴⁴ i.e. personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation. Often called sensitive data.

⁴⁵ Christopher Kuner (n 27)

⁴⁶ Kuru (n 9).

2. Mixed datasets should not be treated as special category data simply by association, as this “inflation” effect may bring a devaluation of the concept.⁴⁷

The case for treating all processed data as special category data derives from two central pillars. First, case 184/20 (OT judgment)⁴⁸ broadened the interpretation of what can be considered special category data. Here, the court ruled that, on top of the Art.9 exhaustive list, if personal data indirectly discloses one’s sexual orientation, said data will be considered special category data by inference. This could be the name of a spouse, cohabitee or partner of a data subject. Two combined datasets, when published online, could generate information considered sensitive. Therefore, given the vast amount of non-sensitive and (potentially) sensitive data, the conclusion was that all data should be considered sensitive. Second, it lies in the *Meta v. Bundeskartellamt*⁴⁹ judgment, where the court ruled that when a processing activity contains both sensitive and non-sensitive data and those are intrinsically intertwined, the entire dataset shall be considered special category data subject to Art. 9 GDPR.

On the other hand, it is noteworthy that some inferences can be considered an overreach or an overgeneralization. In the case cited in the OT judgment for example, where they considered that a name automatically discloses someone’s sexual orientation, this is entirely based on preconceptions, and it disregards edge cases. It could happen that the name of someone’s spouse is “Taylor”, a name that it is used often for both genders; or it could be that someone has a name often used for the opposite gender, simply because their parents decided so; or a name that in different cultures it is used for different genders. The same goes for the hypothesis where a name would automatically disclose someone’s ethnicity, as it is incorrect to assume that all “Muhammads” are muslim, or that all “Kazuyas” are Japanese. Thus, the argument that such datasets would disclose special category data in itself does not sustain itself.

Furthermore, it is important to highlight that intention matters. Even though non-sensitive data could indirectly lead to an inference that is classified as sensitive data, the UK DPA, ICO⁵⁰, is of the opinion that Art. 9 will only be triggered if the processing was performed with a clear intention of making an inference to link a non-sensitive dataset to a sensitive one; or if there is an intention in treating someone differently based on the inferred information. In the case of

⁴⁷ Paul Quinn and Giancarlo Malgieri, ‘The Difficulty of Defining Sensitive Data — The Concept of Sensitive Data in the EU Data Protection Framework’ (2021) 22 German Law Journal 1583 <<https://doi.org/10.1017/glj.2021.79>> accessed 23 August 2025.

⁴⁸ CJEU, Case C-184/20 *OT v Vyriausioji tarnybinės etikos komisija* ECLI:EU:C:2022:601, judgment of 1 August 2022.

⁴⁹ *Meta v Bundeskartellamt* (n 8).

⁵⁰ Information Commissioner’s Office, ‘What is Special Category Data?’ (updated 9 April 2024) <<https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/lawful-basis/special-category-data/what-is-special-category-data/>> accessed 23 August 2025.

general-purpose models, where there is generally no direct intention of making such inference and where in most cases sensitive data is in fact collected incidentally and residually, the inference logic should not apply.

Moreover, the scholars defending that mixed datasets should not be treated as special category data by association, argue that this adds an unnecessary burden to controllers, due to higher regulatory responsibilities. This could subsequently incur a higher risk for circumvention of sensitive data protection rules where safeguards are high. Another risk is of potential “inflation” of sensitive data where the additional tools and safeguards often awarded only to sensitive data could become weakened by the *status quo*. When such exercises become the norm, there is a risk that they will be oversimplified and reduced to tick box exercises and automated assessments; otherwise, controllers would not be able to deal with the hurdle, especially in a time of resource constraints. Either something is special or nothing is.

This author is of the opinion that the position against bundling is the strongest one. Of course, where possible, the controller must make an effort to identify special category data and provide the appropriate safeguards, such as automatic exclusion of sensitive data that is not relevant, or by applying filters to exclude the collection of certain categories of data or even exclude certain sites containing sensitive data by nature before deploying web scraping.⁵¹ However, where it cannot, it does not necessarily mean all Art. 9 restrictions should apply. Finally, it is paramount to consider the intentions of the controller and the purpose of processing.

3.2 Search engines x LLMs: does CJEU C-136/17 apply?

In addition to cases where sensitive data is collected incidentally and residually, there is, in fact, one use case where general-purpose model providers collect that data on purpose, and this is when it comes to public figures. Models such as ChatGPT and Gemini are a vast repository of public information and to be useful to its users it needs to be able to answer certain questions such as ‘who is the current president of the United States and to which political party he is affiliated?’ or ‘what did the queen of England die of?’ or ‘what is Buddha’s most emblematic quote?’. Answers to these questions will certainly contain direct identifiers (e.g. names) and political opinions, religious affiliations, and health information. Here there is no

⁵¹ CNIL, ‘IA : Assurer que le traitement est licite – Définir une base légale’ (updated 8 April 2024) <<https://www.cnil.fr/fr/assurer-que-le-traitement-est-licite>> accessed 23 August 2025.

denying that these are special category data. So, in this scenario, what legal basis should be used?

The CJEU has already faced a similar question in the case *GC and Others v. CNIL*.⁵² In this judgment, it was decided whether the right to be forgotten and Article 9 GDPR applied to search engines when linking to press articles of public figures which contained sensitive information. While the press articles are covered by journalist exemption, the same is not valid for search engines. The problematic was that none of Article 9(2) applied or were feasible to be implemented in this context. Applying Article 9 in full would be prohibitive for search engines, as it would require ex-ante control where they would need to vet upfront every single link to internet pages before referencing them, which, according to the advocate general, Maciej Szpunar, was neither possible nor desirable.

It was a similar conundrum to the one from the *Google Spain* case.⁵³ The search engines have a unique setup where they are not themselves the cause for the personal data to appear in the referenced pages, but only intervene ex-post, also to avoid prior censorship situations. Therefore, the decision in case C-136/17 was in the sense that the prohibition from Article 9 only applies by reason of referencing and via verification on request of a data subject for dereferencing. In which case, the search engine shall verify if it has a valid exemption to process, such as Art. 9(2)(g) GDPR, where processing is necessary for substantial public interest based on EU or member state law. According to the CJEU, this would be linked to the rights of freedom of expression and information (based on Art. 11 EU Charter of Fundamental Rights).⁵⁴

Noteworthy, the de-referencing approach solves not only the legal basis problem, but also data collected *en bloc* issue discussed in the previous subchapter. This mechanism permits an individual evaluation of the nature of each dataset and its correct classification into ordinary personal data or special category personal data, without relying on inferences or simply association. Therefore, in the context of search engines, for ordinary personal data the *Google Spain* case applies, while for the special category personal data case C-136/17 applies.

When considering emerging technologies, search engines and generative AI chatbots e.g. ChatGPT (not LLMs models themselves, which are much more powerful and multifunctional) are not so different. They are often used for the same purpose (i.e. search for information), and

⁵² *GC and Others v CNIL* (n 11).

⁵³ CJEU, Case C-131/12 *Google Spain SL and Google Inc v AEPD and Mario Costeja González* (Grand Chamber, 13 May 2014).

⁵⁴ *GC and Others v CNIL* (n 11).

both contain a database that can be used to find this data. However, they have one key difference between them. While search engines' index systems work with dynamic crawling⁵⁵ ChatGPT has static databases. This means that while the search engine crawlers revisit pages periodically (based on page importance and popularity) and update their index database frequently and automatically, ChatGPT is trained with information until up to a certain period in time (e.g. September 2024). For example, if a newspaper deletes an article, the link may persist in the search engine index for a short while, but it will eventually be deleted. However, if a user clicks on said link, it will be directed to a page without any content, e.g. error 404 or content not found. On the contrary, even if an article is deleted from the internet, the static database from ChatGPT will still retain that information unless the model is trained or fine-tuned with new information. Furthermore, even without considering the advantage of dynamic crawlers and automatic updates, the operation of deindexing personal data after a data subject request (ex post) is also a much simpler operation than removing data from an LLM.

Therefore, this CJEU decision can only be applied in an analogous manner⁵⁶, if similar controls can be put in place, in a way that generative AI chatbots can have access to up-to-date information and remove information that should no longer be there from their knowledge base. Such a topic has had quite a lot of attention from computer scientists in the past few years, with some interesting proposals surfacing. The first of them is Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG)⁵⁷ which allows for initially static AI models to fetch external data at query time. A model with such a feature can retrieve relevant information from trusted sources (like a vector database or web index), then uses it to generate its answers; that way, it can circumvent limitations like only having access to old information, leading to hallucinations or a lack of responses. This also allowed systems such as ChatGPT to be able to provide the source of their research to users for real-time verification of information.

Yet, issues with the removal of information remain. Retraining models and machine unlearning techniques are quite time and resource intensive and are not appropriate to adhere to constant requests for data deletion. For that we can use a novel approach called Dynamic Sparse Knowledge Attention (DySK-Attn) proposed by a paper from August 2025. DySK-Attn

⁵⁵ Google, 'How Search Works' (2024) <<https://www.google.com/search/howsearchworks/>> accessed 23 August 2025.

"Google downloads a copy of the pages from all the web, scans it and makes a list of all the words and list of all the pages each word appears on. It's like the index of a book."

⁵⁶ Lokke Moerel and Marijn Storm, 'Using Special Categories of Data for Training LLMs: Never Allowed?' IAPP (28 August 2024) <<https://iapp.org/news/a/using-special-categories-of-data-for-training-llms-never-allowed-/>> accessed 23 August 2025.

⁵⁷ Patrick Lewis and others, 'Retrieval-Augmented Generation for Knowledge-Intensive NLP Tasks' (2020) arXiv <<https://arxiv.org/abs/2005.11401>> accessed 23 August 2025.

approach is of building a Knowledge Graph (KG) outside the model, instead of relying solely on the internal database and static weights. By using this sparse attention layer (e.g. in lay terms, a spotlight), the LLM will focus only on the relevant fresh nodes. So, if the graph updates (when a page disappears or information needs to be “dereferenced”), then the spotlight will shift, and the old data will drop out of the attention field, no longer being contained in an output.⁵⁸

It would also be advantageous to this approach, embedding a crawler (like the ones used by search engines) into the model pipeline to gather updates and notices when pages are updated, and pushing these updates into the KG or vector database that feeds the model. Then, a “right to be forgotten” signal could be triggered whenever a “dereferencing” request is received, or the crawler detects that a webpage has been deleted. The corresponding node will be deleted or masked in the KG/vector database, and next time the model reaches out to the KG, that information will already be automatically “deleted” (out of the spotlight). See the flowchart below⁵⁹:

With that set up in place, the Art. 9 prohibition applies to the operators of search engines and generative AI chatbots only within the scope of their responsibilities, power and possibilities. This position is also supported by CNIL, which states in its guidelines that if

⁵⁸ Kabir Khan and others, ‘DySK-Attn: A Framework for Efficient, Real-Time Knowledge Updating in Large Language Models via Dynamic Sparse Knowledge Attention’ (arXiv, 10 August 2025) <<https://arxiv.org/abs/2508.07185>> accessed 23 August 2025.

⁵⁹ Flowchart created by Artificial Intelligence. Tool used: ChatGPT. Model: 5. Date: 25/08/2025. Prompt: “Let’s try to work together on a technical measure that works for LLMs. Manually retraining or fine tuning a model every time a web page containing personal data disappears or changes does not seem feasible. Is there a way to embed into a LLM the same type of dynamic crawler that a search engine has to update their database in real-time? How would that work and has someone proposed that already? If not a crawler, would it be possible, whenever someone asks a question about a link that is no longer functioning, the LLM could automatically learn from that and update its database with that accurate information?”.

organizations incidentally and residually process sensitive data they did not seek to collect, this is not automatically considered illegal.⁶⁰

Thus, the prohibitions will apply to a generative AI chatbot provider if the sensitive data is in the output of the system and subject to ex-post verification based on the request of an individual. They can also invoke Article 9(2)(g) exception for when the data is retained and rely on freedom of information as well.⁶¹

In fact, ChatGPT updated its privacy policy in 2024 to refer to the legitimate interest of the broader society in its processing activities related to training ChatGPT. They also state on their data subjects request page that every request will be verified considering the balance between data protection rights and public interests like access to information, which displays willingness to make use of this exception.⁶² Nonetheless, to fully implement this exception an appropriate governance framework needs to be put in place, as these measures are not sufficient. If they will in fact pursue it further, it is still unknown.

3.3 Manifestly made public

In case C-136/17, CJEU also explicitly acknowledges that Article 9(2)(e) might be a fitting exception for the search engine use case.⁶³ This could be applicable to use cases where the data controller might want to collect sensitive data beyond public figures and where freedom of information might not apply.

To apply the manifestly made public exception, three key elements must be present:

- Manifestly: explicit, affirmative act by the data subject or confirmation that they realized what would be the result. For example, entering the range of a camera in a public or private space does not mean the data subject intends to make their sensitive data available to the public⁶⁴;
- Making public: data must be realistically accessible to the general public, for example by publishing the data in the mass media e.g. via social network platforms, blog posts, articles authored by the data subject.⁶⁵ Disclosures to a particular

⁶⁰ CNIL (n 51).

⁶¹ Moerel and Storm (n 56).

⁶² Kuru (n 9).

⁶³ Ibid.

⁶⁴ European Data Protection Board, *Guidelines 3/2019 on Processing of Personal Data through Video Devices* (29 January 2020) 15 <https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/guidelines/guidelines-32019-processing-personal-data-through-video_en> accessed 27 August 2025; *Meta v Bundeskartellamt* (n 8).

⁶⁵ *Kuner and others* (n 27).

audience, or just because one individual has access to it does not qualify.⁶⁶ For example, if a post was meant to be shared only with family and friends, in a private social media account (not accessible to non-followers/connections), this requirement cannot be considered met. According to the EDPB this data also cannot have been made public illegally⁶⁷;

- By the data subject: data must be published by the data subject themselves. It cannot simply be published directly by a third party (e.g. a friend, a journalist) or inferred (e.g. ethnicity inferred from a photo). A photo where the data subject was tagged, but that was originally posted by a friend, would not be sufficient.⁶⁸

While these requirements are quite strict, by relying on ex-post verification and using the de-referencing mechanism, it is possible to assess each individual case for suitability with those elements. Otherwise, a bulk analysis of the requirements will most certainly result in a negative assessment of its application. Given the residual and incidental nature of the data collection shared by both the search engine use and the generative AI chatbot use case, it is possible to apply again case C-136/17 analogously, if the aforementioned mitigation measures are applied.

However, there are other use cases that do not fall under the scope of case C-136/17 and therefore, must be evaluated in bulk. Therefore, for the purposes of this work, the applicability of the manifestly made public exception in the following use case will also be analyzed:

Controller purposefully collects special category data to identify individuals.

To discuss this applicability, the Clearview AI case will be in focus.⁶⁹ Clearview is a United States (U.S) based company that provides facial recognition services to law enforcement agencies. To create their database, they scraped over 20 billion photos and selfies from all over the internet and used them to train their facial recognition software. This technology allowed an individual (i.e. law enforcement agent) to upload a photo of a person of interest or a suspect, which would then be compared against the Clearview database. The software was impressive, due to its exceptionally high accuracy rate, even in situations where someone's face was partially covered or a person's face was in the background.

⁶⁶ Information Commissioner's Office (UK), 'What are the Conditions for Processing?' (updated 2024) <<https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/lawful-basis/criminal-offence-data/what-are-the-conditions-for-processing/>> accessed 23 August 2025.

⁶⁷ EDPB (n 64).

⁶⁸ European Data Protection Board, *Guidelines 08/2020 on the Targeting of Social Media Users* (13 April 2021) <https://www.edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/guidelines/guidelines-82020-targeting-social-media-users_en> accessed 27 August 2025.

⁶⁹ Clearview AI, Homepage (2025) <<https://www.clearview.ai/>> accessed 27 August 2025.

However, their company has not reached global headlines because of its great capabilities, but rather due to its questionable privacy practices. Back in 2020, a New York Times journalist published an exposé⁷⁰ shedding light on Clearview's indiscriminate data collection and calling out the risks of having such a powerful tool in one's hands. Although photos are not considered sensitive data by default, whenever they are used for authentication, they fall into the biometric data category, hence sensitive data. The nature of this processing could incur significant risks for data subjects, which led to a wave of fines by DPAs all over the world.⁷¹

Clearview argued that they only collected data from publicly available sources, just like search engines, thereby implicitly relying on Art. 9(2)(e) exception. However, for use cases with such a vast scale of processing and heteronomous dataset and collected purposefully, it becomes virtually impossible to adequately fit the requirements.

Therefore, as stated in the reasoning of many DPA fines against Clearview AI, they failed to meet those requirements. This was also not a case of incidental collection. Clearview AI aimed to process datasets that would not meet the requirements, as this was the best way to reach images of people with a small or almost non-existent digital footprint, for example, using tagged photos posted by friends as a way to find pictures of individuals who never post anything on social media.

Finally, unlike generative AI chatbots, Clearview AI cannot be placed in the same category as search engines and should not benefit from the same *de facto* exception recognized in the case C-136/17. Despite Clearview's allegations, they are not “Google for faces”. They are fundamentally different in:

- Nature of data: Clearview AI’s core business depends exclusively on processing biometric data, which is classified as a special category of personal data under Art. 9 GDPR. Search engines, by contrast, only incidentally encounter such data when crawling the open web. The difference between “residual exposure” and “systematic exploitation” of sensitive data is significant;

⁷⁰ Kashmir Hill, ‘The Secretive Company That Might End Privacy as We Know It’ *The New York Times* (18 January 2020) <<https://www.nytimes.com/2020/01/18/technology/clearview-privacy-facial-recognition.html>> accessed 27 August 2025.

⁷¹ Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens, *Decision Imposing Administrative Fine on Clearview AI* (16 May 2024) <<https://www.autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl/en/system/files?file=2024-09%2FDecision+finer+and+orders+subject+to+a+penalty+Clearview.pdf>> accessed 25 August 2025; CNIL, *Délibération de la formation restreinte n° SAN-2022-019 concernant CLEARVIEW AI* (17 October 2022) <https://www.cnil.fr/sites/default/files/atoms/files/deliberation_of_the_restricted_committee_no_san-2022-019_of_17_october_2022_concerning_clearview_ai.pdf> accessed 27 August 2025; Information Commissioner’s Office, ‘Information Commissioner Seeks Permission to Appeal Clearview AI Inc Tribunal Ruling’ (17 November 2023) <<https://ico.org.uk/about-the-ico/media-centre/news-and-blogs/2023/11/information-commissioner-seeks-permission-to-appeal-clearview-ai-inc-ruling/>> accessed 27 August 2025.

- Purpose of processing: search engines provide a general tool for information retrieval across all domains of knowledge, while Clearview AI has a single, narrow function: identifying individuals. This shift from knowledge facilitation to surveillance transforms the risk level entirely.
- Risk to data subjects: the consequences of having data indexed by a search engine are not comparable to being permanently enrolled in a facial recognition database. One exposes information that is already public; the other extracts biometric identifiers in a way that makes opting out practically impossible. The imbalance of power, coupled with the irreversibility of biometric data misuse, places Clearview AI in a distinct and far more intrusive category.

Thus, the analogy to search engines collapses. Case C-136/17 did not create a free pass for any technology that indexes data; it weighed the proportionality of the specific functions and risks. On those terms, Clearview AI cannot be paired with search engines or generative AI chatbots.

4. Building a governance model for legitimate interest

Whenever a new regulation or technology surfaces many discussions on how to achieve compliance or if that is even possible come to light. Could there be a more privacy-friendly way to process data? If the solution has not shown itself yet, it might simply mean individuals need to be more creative, pioneers.

Cookie banners and Consent Management Platforms (CMPs) are a great example of that. The ePrivacy Directive requirement coined in 2002 was simply that the legal basis to process data through tracking technologies (e.g. cookies) needed to be consent, unless the processing was strictly necessary.⁷² There was nothing in its text explaining or limiting what method should be used for that purpose. Cookie banners and CMPs were a technical solution created by industry to comply with the law and nowadays are used as a global standard for such practices. Any other method could have been chosen (and it still can), as long as it fits Art. 5(3) requirement.

In the LLM space there are already initiatives actively tackling current regulatory compliance gaps, in search of a better path forward. That is the case for the open source LLM

⁷² European Parliament and Council, Directive 2002/58/EC of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (Directive on privacy and electronic communications) [2002] OJ L201/37, art 5(3).

built by a partnership between the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (ETH Zurich) and the Federal Polytechnic School of Lausanne (EPFL). This LLM was trained on the Alps supercomputer at the Swiss National Supercomputing Centre (CSCS).

*“The model will be fully open: source code and weights will be publicly available, and the training data will be transparent and reproducible, supporting adoption across science, government, education, and the private sector. This approach is designed to foster both innovation and accountability. Fully open models enable high-trust applications and are necessary for advancing research about the risks and opportunities of AI. Transparent processes also enable regulatory compliance.”*⁷³

This new alternative is not only a good step towards innovation, but it also addresses concerns with data protection, copyrights and AI laws. Interestingly, a 2025 study showed that respecting web crawling opt-outs during data collection produces almost no performance degradation for models used for most daily tasks and a general knowledge repository.⁷⁴

Having that as background, this chapter aims to propose solutions to the most common clashes between LLM technology and data protection principles.

4.1 Data minimization and filtering

The first issue concerns Art. 5(1)(c) GDPR, the principle of data minimization. LLMs are known for needing exorbitant amounts of data to be trained on. To predict well, it needs to have seen enough examples and variations of contexts. If the dataset happens to be too small, the model may overfit (memorize data instead of generalizing it)⁷⁵, which leads to problems when faced with new situations, as it cannot adapt itself properly.

While it is difficult to draw a line on how much data is necessary to fulfill the purposes of processing without assessing it case-by-case, what can be applicable generically are boundary

⁷³ European University Association (ETH Zurich Corporate Communications and EPFL AI Communication), ‘A Language Model Built for the Public Good’ (ETH News, 9 July 2025) <<https://ethz.ch/en/news-and-events/eth-news/news/2025/07/a-language-model-built-for-the-public-good.html>> accessed 27 August 2025.

⁷⁴ Dongyang Fan and others, ‘Can Performant LLMs Be Ethical? Quantifying the Impact of Web Crawling Opt-Outs’ (arXiv, 5 August 2025) <<https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.06219>> accessed 28 August 2025.

⁷⁵ European Cloud Federation, ‘Overfitting: A Conversation Starter for the Next Summer Party’ (n 7); European Commission, *Deep Dive into Artificial Intelligence and Data Ecosystems – Fundamental Rights, Ethics and Data Protection* (n 7).

measures to avoid the collection of unnecessary data. CNIL has put together quite a useful list⁷⁶:

- Define, upstream, the precise collection criteria;
- Exclude certain categories of data from the collection. This can be done through filters on specific types of data (e.g. bank details, geolocation, health data; children’s data; pseudonyms); or filtering websites that contain content that is not relevant to the purposes of the LLM (e.g. pornographic websites, patient discussion forums, websites in languages not supported by the LLM);
- Exclude from the scope sites that clearly oppose the harvesting of their content. This can be done by the implementation of CAPTCHAs (which can already be circumvented by AI Agents); using Do-Not-Train data designation like robots.txt or ai.txt exclusion protocols⁷⁷; or including language in the website’s Terms and Conditions (T&Cs);
- Exclude private profiles in social media networks and content under a paywall;
- Use anonymized, pseudonymized or synthetic data as an alternative if possible.

Following these proposed mitigation measures, the risk of unnecessary data collection can be reduced considerably, as well it may help companies to also avoid issues with copyright law and AI regulations, as these can be considered responsible AI practices.⁷⁸

4.2 Transparency and documentation

On the topic of transparency, Arts. 12-14 GDPR⁷⁹ make it clear that the controller must provide transparency information to data subjects on how their data is being collected. This is often done via a Privacy Notice on a website or an application (app), and it can also be done by direct interaction with the data subject through checkboxes and pop-ups. However, the situation is considerably more complicated when there is no direct relationship between the data subject and the controller and where the personal data has not been obtained directly from the data subject, such as in the case of web scraping.

⁷⁶ CNIL, ‘La base légale de l’intérêt légitime: fiche focus sur les mesures à prendre en cas de collecte des données par moissonnage (web scraping)’ (19 June 2025) <<https://www.cnil.fr/fr/focus-interet-legitime-collecte-par-moissonnage>> accessed 28 August 2025.

⁷⁷ Transparency Coalition, ‘TCAI Urges Adoption of “Do Not Train” Data and Training Data Request Prompts’ (12 December 2025) <<https://www.transparencycoalition.ai/news/tcai-urges-adoption-of-do-not-train-data-new-training-data-request-prompts>> accessed 29 August 2025.

⁷⁸ IBM, ‘What is Responsible AI?’ <<https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/responsible-ai>> accessed 28 August 2025.

⁷⁹ GDPR (n 5) arts 12–14.

According to Art. 14 GDPR, the data subject shall be informed within a reasonable period of time after the controller obtained their personal data (but at the latest within one month) and must receive full information about the source of the collection, how the data will be processed, as well as their related rights. This obligation will not be applicable only in case (i) the data subject already has the information; (ii) where providing such information proves impossible or would involve a disproportionate effort; (iii) where obtaining or disclosure is expressly regulated via Union or Member State law; or (iv) where the data must remain confidential due to an obligation of professional secrecy.

One may argue that obtaining such a vast pool of personal data from various sources would render such transparency impossible or a disproportionate effort to the LLM provider. It could even be that the information collected does not include the contact details necessary to reach out to data subjects. Nevertheless, this argument does not hold up. First, one must be careful not to interpret GDPR in a manner that distorts its intended protection purposes.

The Polish DPA decision in the Bisnode case illustrates that quite well. In this case, a digital marketing company scraped credit-related personal data, including phone numbers and addresses from public registers, and although it has a Privacy Notice in its website explaining the processing, it did not reach out to the data subjects directly to notify them of the collection. What happens is that without knowing about this processing, data subjects might never spontaneously go to their website to get informed. While the DPA concluded that there was no disproportionate effort to inform the data subjects, the Polish court amended the decision to the extent that for data subjects for whom the controller had no contact details, the notification was in fact disproportionate. Decisions such as this one might lead to data scrapers deliberately avoiding datasets that contain contact details, to circumvent the transparency obligation.⁸⁰

Second, the topic of transparency is no longer a GDPR only concern. Art.53(1)(d) EU AI Act also stipulates that providers of general-purpose AI models, shall make their training sources available to the public:

“(1) Providers of general-purpose AI models shall: (d) draw up and make publicly available a sufficiently detailed summary about the content used for training of the general-purpose AI model, according to a template provided by the AI Office.”⁸¹

⁸⁰ Akshita Rohatgi and Tae Jung Park, ‘Privacy in the Public: Analysing the EU Framework to Outline Approaches for Regulating AI Personal Data Scraping’ (2025) Computer Law & Security Review 57 <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2025.106150>> accessed 28 August 2025.

⁸¹ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (Artificial Intelligence Act) [2024] OJ L1689, art 53(1)(d).

The template recently provided by the AI Office on July 24th, 2025, is an invaluable asset when it comes to transparency about training aspects, and it includes the requirement to list the top 10% of all domain names determined by the size of the scraped content. This provision also applies to Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), including start-ups, where those should disclose the top 5% of all domain names or 1000 internet domain names, whichever is lower. Such template shall be made available in a prominent space of the general-purpose provider, as at the bottom on the website page (like a Privacy Notice or Cookie Policy) and/or in a Trust Center.⁸²

Although direct communication with data subjects might indeed not be possible, LLM providers should invest in mass media campaigns to inform society in general that their data might have been scraped for AI training and drive them towards their websites, where they can find more detailed information in the Privacy Notice and in the Public Summary of training content. While the list does not contain the full list of sources (only the top 10%), mechanisms should be made available to data subjects to request more information or ask directly about a specific source/domain. Frequent Asked Questions (FAQ) documents and explanatory videos are encouraged. controllers must avoid spreading the information through many different subpages, as this may be considered too burdensome or too confusing for the data subject to find.⁸³

⁸² European Commission, *Explanatory Notice and Template for the Public Summary of Training Content for General-Purpose AI Models* (AI Office, 24 July 2025) <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/explanatory-notice-and-template-public-summary-training-content-general-purpose-ai-models>> accessed 28 August 2025.

⁸³ Ruth Boardman, 'Irish DPC WhatsApp Decision: What Do You Need to Know?' IAPP (28 September 2021) <<https://iapp.org/news/a/irish-dpc-whatsapp-decision-what-do-you-need-to-know>> accessed 28 August 2025.

2.3. Data crawled and scraped from online sources

This section requires information about crawled, scraped data, otherwise compiled from online sources directly by the provider of the model or on their behalf (i.e. excluding publicly available datasets already compiled by third parties and made available on platforms such as common crawl that are covered under Section 2.1).

Were crawlers used by the provider or on behalf of?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
If yes, specify crawler name(s)/identifier(s):	
Purposes of the crawler(s):	
General description of crawler behaviour:	<i>For example, this includes respect of captchas, password protected websites and paywalls, respect of robot.txt and other protocols, while crawling.</i>
Period of data collection:	<i>From MM/YYYY to MM/YYYY</i>
Comprehensive description of the type of content and online sources crawled:	<i>Provide a comprehensive description of the type of content crawled, including its geographical, linguistic or demographic characteristics, as well as an indication of the type of websites scraped (e.g. news, blogs, social media, forums, community websites, other user-generated content platforms, websites of cultural heritage institutions, educational sites, government portals, personal blogs, streaming, gaming platforms, online TV platforms, synthetic data libraries, etc).</i>
Type of modality covered:	<input type="checkbox"/> Text <input type="checkbox"/> Image <input type="checkbox"/> Video <input type="checkbox"/> Audio <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
Summary of the most relevant domain names crawled:	<i>In so far as any content from internet domains has been crawled or scraped and used for the training of the model, provide a list of those most relevant internet domains names (top and second-level domain, e.g. "example.com") by listing the top 10 % of all domain names determined by the size of the content scraped (in a representative manner across all modalities where applicable). Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), including start-ups, should disclose top 5% of all domain names or 1 000 internet domain names, whichever is lower. You can provide this list for instance as a downloadable file or provide here information on how to access it.</i>
Additional comments (optional):	<i>Providers may also disclose other relevant information on a voluntary basis, for instance more domain names than those required in the list above and/or URLs and the sources of individual works.</i>

FIGURE 2. PARTIAL SCREENSHOT OF THE TEMPLATE FOR THE PUBLIC SUMMARY OF TRAINING CONTENT FOR GENERAL-PURPOSE AI MODELS REQUIRED BY ARTICLE 53 (1)(D) OF REGULATION (EU) 2024/1689 (AI ACT)

Regarding documentation, it is also paramount to perform a Legitimate Interest Assessment (LIA) and a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA). Those should preferably be made available upfront as part of a Trust Portal (with redactions where appropriate), but as a fallback, they must be made available to data subjects if requested.

4.3 Data subject rights

Finally, when it comes to data subject rights and requests, this is really the place where pioneering and innovative approaches are most required. Current technical solutions, even the

one proposed for “de-referencing” by using an additional layer and the spotlight approach (DySK-Attn), are not fully compliant with GDPR. Any type of filtering techniques, techniques that prevent personal data from being displayed as an output to an AI system, while valid and necessary mitigation measures, are not enough, because in the end of the day, the personal data remains inside the model and an action as simple as reframing a question might trigger the appearance of the personal data again. The same goes for requests for correction; depending on the relationship between the nodes inside the model, it might be that the personal data is not fully fixed. For example, one may alter the answer to the prompt “The last name of the president of the USA is?” from Trump to Macron. However, if someone asks in a different prompt, “Americans elected a president with the last name”, the LLM might still revert to the original answer, Trump.⁸⁴

Therefore, the ideal approach would be to re-train the model, fine-tune it and apply machine unlearning techniques. Still, the computational costs and efforts are prohibitive to implement for every single request. That is why machine unlearning techniques must be further developed and refined to the point that the controller can fully fulfil a request, rather than simply applying a mitigation measure. CNIL, in its guidelines, also emphasizes that the development of technical solutions is encouraged, not only to fulfil deletion and correction requests, but also to provide the possibility to exercise the right to object upstream of data collection. “Push list” mechanisms could be implemented, allowing the controller to respect the opposition of individuals by refraining collection of their data in the first place.⁸⁵

As a last point, controllers must have a facilitated and transparent mechanism for data subjects to exercise their rights. This should also be available to data subjects who are not platform users but might have had their data processed for training purposes. Communication and a mass media campaign is essential in this context as well.

5. Conclusion

This thesis proposes to answer three main questions.

First, can legitimate interest under Article 6(1)(f) GDPR serve as a lawful basis for training AI models on personal data? This debate was covered in Chapter 2. There, all legal bases under

⁸⁴ Henrik Nolte, Michèle Finck and Kristof Meding, ‘Machine Learners Should Acknowledge the Legal Implications of Large Language Models as Personal Data’ (arXiv, 18 June 2025) <<https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.01630>> accessed 28 August 2025.

⁸⁵ CNIL (n 76).

Article 6(1) GDPR were analyzed for its applicability under the context of a controller collecting vast datasets of ordinary personal data to train LLMs. While some were not applicable due to the nature of the processing, others proved to be unfeasible to be implemented in a practical scenario, either because of technical limitations (consent management of data subjects to which the controller had no direct relationship) or because of an overall societal rejection of this type of processing.

While legitimate interest was the only residual choice, and also the choice made by all major LLM providers, it was established that this is not enough reason to use it as a legal basis, nor does it make said use compliant. A 3-step test must be performed to ascertain that the interest is lawful, necessary and does not override data subjects' freedoms and rights. All other GDPR principles are also in interplay and must be taken into consideration. Another important aspect is that training AI systems is not the purpose of processing in itself, the real end use of the tool should be the one evaluated. Although it might be challenging to define a single purpose for a general-purpose model, one may argue that, enabling its users to access information quickly and in a more digestible manner, fits the scope.

The legal basis of legitimate interest was also assessed for its applicability in use cases where the controller re-purposes a company's large-scale dataset of ordinary personal data to train an internal general-purpose LLM. The Meta use case was used as a paradigm for this analysis. The overall conclusion, for both use cases, was that legitimate interest may apply to them, as long as the controller properly addresses other GDPR principles and implements adequate mitigation measures.

Second, considering that legitimate interest does not apply to special category data, what alternatives can be put in place for this type of processing? This debate was carried out in Chapter 3. In order to answer, at first an additional question needed to be posed of whether all data collected via web scraping should be considered special category data. Between two antagonistic views from scholars, the negative prevailed. The rationale was that bundling all personal data into special category data adds unnecessary burden to controllers, and the "inflation" of sensitive data could lead to oversimplification of assessments and tick box exercises.

Additionally, it was discussed whether the CJEU C-136/17 case could be analogously applied to generative AI chatbots due to its similarity to search engines. While the purposes of use might be the same (i.e. knowledge repository), the technologies work quite in a different manner. To implement a "de-referencing" request into a separate database embedded in what

the LLM learned during the training phase, a lot more technical work must be considered. Therefore, application of the ex-post mechanism to generative AI chatbots is possible, but only if mitigation measures to allow for such a request fulfillment are put in place. Article 9(2)(e) exception, data manifestly made public, was also assessed both in the scope of generative AI chatbots, as well as for facial recognition software. For the latter the use case was Clearview AI. The exception is quite a restrictive one and carries several cumulative requirements that are virtually impossible to fulfill by performing a bulk analysis of such a large-scale dataset. On the question of whether CJEU C-136/17 could apply to Clearview, the conclusion was also negative, as the nature and purpose of processing were fundamentally different.

Third, which mitigation measures (including obligations under the AI Act) should be implemented for a privacy compliant governance framework? CNIL has been quite active when it comes to the intersection of privacy and AI technology. Its guidelines provide a practical overview of data minimization measures, transparency approaches, as well as how to proceed with data subject requests. Noteworthy, that when it comes to transparency, other regulations must be considered, beyond GDPR. Art. 53(1)(d) of the EU AI Act states that general-purpose AI model providers must make information about the training sources publicly available. This must be done in accordance with a template provided by the AI Office. On the other hand, while there are a lot of uncertainties, when it comes to technical measures to implement data subject requests, several mitigation measures provide a promising way forward.

Ultimately, while the rapid evolution of AI leaves questions towards its compatibility with current regulatory instruments, there is already a solid base of guidance and jurisprudence that can be used analogously to fill in the gaps. In the meantime, controllers are encouraged to keep aiming for more privacy-friendly solutions and new creative ideas to address the technical challenges posed at this time. Looking optimistically towards the future, these ideas will soon become the industry standard and best practices, and scholars will be able to move on to the next challenging questions.

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